

REINCARNATE

BIM for Circular Value Flow Planning, Demo case: Flat glass to flat glass

Innovation + Demo Case

Technical Deep-Dive Report

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Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains.

All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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CVFP – Circular Value Flow Planning

Figure 1. The circular life of flat glass. Glass in existing buildings is removed to be circulated and weighed. The glass is separated from other materials during pretreatment. The cullet is weighed and quality assured and weighed. It is now raw material and not a waste. The raw material is melted into new flat glass, which can be used to produce new windows. These new windows are mounted in buildings, and the loop is closed.

1. Executive summary

This technical deep-dive presents the innovation BIM for Circular Value Flow Planning (BIM-CVFP) through the demonstration case “Flat glass to flat glass,” conducted within the REINCARNATE project. The objective is to enable high-quality circular material flows in the construction sector by integrating physical recycling processes with structured, traceable data flows. The demonstration follows windows from a real building scheduled for demolition, documenting their dismantling, transport, pre-treatment, quality assurance, and conversion into cullet for manufacturing new flat glass products. A central focus is the use of inventory data, enterprise system information, and weight measurements to verify material quantities and traceability across the value chain. Results show that approximately 91% of recovered glass could be recycled into new flat glass, demonstrating significant environmental and resource-efficiency potential.

The case also evaluates the accuracy of different inventory methods and highlights the importance of standardized data collection and interoperability for circular planning. Overall, the demonstration provides a replicable, data-driven model that addresses key barriers to circular construction: fragmented information, lack of traceability, and limited decision support, while illustrating the practical feasibility of closed-loop recycling for flat glass.

2. Context and objectives

Efforts to enable circular material flows in the construction sector are currently constrained by significant data and information limitations. In Sweden, pre-demolition audits are legally required to evaluate the reuse potential of building components before renovation or demolition. However, the legislation does not define standardized methodologies or mandatory data fields, resulting in inconsistent practices and varying data quality among auditors. At the European level, the EU Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol similarly recommends such audits to identify hazardous materials and reuse opportunities, but does not prescribe detailed procedures or standardized data structures.

In addition, both Swedish and EU waste statistics rely on the European Waste Catalogue (EWC) classification system, which groups materials into broad waste categories. This aggregation limits the granularity and comparability of available data, making it difficult to plan and implement circular material flows efficiently. Since circular solutions are expected to be developed and implemented primarily by businesses, harmonized audit methods and more detailed material classification systems would significantly improve the conditions for circular construction.

Another major challenge is the lack of accessible lifecycle information about building materials. While large amounts of documentation are generated during construction and building operation, these records rarely contain

material-level information relevant for reuse or recycling. Furthermore, the data is often not systematically preserved or shared, and there are no standardized protocols for exchanging information between building owners and waste management actors. As a result, datasets remain fragmented and non-interoperable or non-existent, limiting the ability to make informed decisions and develop scalable circular business models.

Consequently, the demonstration “flat glass to flat glass” focuses on enabling circular material flows by illustrating how flat glass recovered from existing buildings can be processed and reintroduced into new window products. The objective is to demonstrate how both physical material flows and structured data flows are required to support circularity across the value chain.

The demonstration evaluates how information generated from building inventories, sensors, external databases, and actors across the value chain can be integrated and shared through the CP-IM platform. By using the structure of a standardized ontology (presented in D1.1 An ontology for circular management of buildings), the demonstrator aims to enable traceability of materials, support circularity assessments, and improve strategic planning of secondary material flows.

Building on the demonstration “inventory of the material bank”, which focuses on collecting and structuring data from existing buildings, this demonstrator addresses the downstream stages of the circular process. It evaluates how well the information collected, using different methods, in the “inventory of the material bank” demonstration maps, against the actual output of the recycling process of flat glass. It also evaluates how standardized data exchange between actors in a value chain can facilitate the recycling of flat glass into new flat glass products.

3. Innovation description

The innovation BIM for circular value flow planning (BIM-CVFP) builds on the concept of Circular value flow planning (CVFP). The aim is to enable better

planning of material flows and thus enable circular material flows and keep material at a high quality in the industrial system as long and qualitatively as possible. BIM for circular value flow planning is enabled by using a BIM model as the facilitator of data collected from the built environment to estimate the amount of material as well as the material quality, and by doing so, enable decision making for increased circularity.

Ragn-Sells is demonstrating the innovation by testing how flat glass from old windows is recycled into new flat glass for windows. The demo “flat glass to flat glass” shows the end of that circle, while the demonstration “inventory of the material bank” demonstrates the initiating phase of the innovation.

In the demonstration “flat glass to flat glass,” we look at both the material flow and the data flow. The data flow is demonstrated by measuring weight at different points in the physical material flow. These data points are then used to calculate the accuracy of the estimates derived from the different methods of collecting data from the built environment in the demonstration “Inventory of the material bank” to the outcome of Ragn-Sells production process.

The material flow across the value chain is demonstrated by the physical handling of the material from Teknikhöjden to the production of the glass cullet being sent for recycling further downstream.

Finally, the operational challenges connected to the specific data and material flow for flat glass recycling are identified and evaluated.

4. Demonstration Setup

Together with Akademiska Hus (property owner), we identified a building that was suitable for demonstrating both the inventory part and the bulk of the material flow of the circular value flow planning module (CVFP). The building chosen to demo “inventory of the material bank” was Teknikhöjden, a building from the 1960s that was scheduled for demolition. The inventory was delimited to windows which made it easier to focus the work and connect to D1.1, which outlines the digital ontology for flat glass.

For this demonstration, “flat glass to flat glass,” the windows from Teknikhögden were used to demonstrate the process as well as the material flow and the data flow needed to enable circular solutions.

4.1 Material flow

Once the inventory step is completed, the windows need to be dismantled and packaged in a way that retains and ensures the window’s structural integrity at the construction site as well as through multiple transportations.

The next step is to transport the windows, placed on pallets, to a pre-treatment facility where the glass is separated from the frame. Once separated, the glass can be sent through a quality assurance plant from which end of wasted glass cullet is produced. In the quality assurance plant, “reject” and “glass <8mm” are separated from the cullet since those streams cannot be used to create new flat glass. The reject, the fraction “<8mm”, and the cullet are then weighted. After the quality assurance, the cullet is defined as a product, packaged in big bags and sent to the glass manufacturer to manufacture new flat glass. The process can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The different steps of the material flow of flat glass recycling.

Due to Teknikhögden’s location in relation to Ragn-Sells treatment facility in Örebro, where glass can be both pre-treated and quality assured, the pallets with windows were sent there.

4.2 Data flow

Traceability of the windows helps enable circular value flows of the windows and is necessary for the End of Waste process. Thus, data needs to be collected throughout the physical material flow. In order to ensure traceability, several data points retrieved from Ragn-Sells ERP are needed, such as customer numbers, customer relationships, and material code. These data points converge into an order number, which is the primary identifier of a specific pick up of windows.

Figure 3: Data points required for traceability on the batch level

Assigning a specific identifier to a delivery of windows is one piece of the puzzle of creating traceability. It answers questions such as “where does the window come from?”

Another piece of the puzzle of creating traceability is material weight, which is measured across the different steps in the physical flow. The main steps of the data collection can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Data points collected at each step of the material flow process

The first weight control, “Vehicle over scale”, is conducted when the truck with windows enters the Ragn-Sells facility in Örebro. Once that is done, the windows might be stored at the facility prior to pre-treatment. To ensure that nothing has changed during the storage time, a “before pre-treatment” check is done just prior to the material being sent through pre-treatment. Since the separated glass ends up in bins during the pre-treatment process, several orders can get mixed in each bin. These are assigned a batch number prior to entering the quality assurance. Consequently, a batch number can include windows from different buildings and customers while acting as a “container” for all order numbers connected to that batch. This means that one can verify the sources of the cullet coming through the quality assurance step.

For this demonstration, the final step of the data flow is to measure the weight of the cullet, “glass <8mm” and the “reject” after pre-treatment, which is then compared with the weight of glass from the estimated weight from the different methods in the demonstration “inventory of the material bank”.

4.3 Connecting to the CP-IM Platform

The material flow combined with the data flow enables tracing the windows from the building to cullet and further into the manufacturing process of new flat glass for windows. The cullet data was intended to be uploaded to Mainflux as part of the CP-IM platform together with external databases for CO₂ calculations. However, this was seen to be a lower TRL and was not implemented in the platform in the end.

As mentioned in the demonstration “inventory of the material bank,” the CVFP-module in the CP-IM platform is to analyze the data provided and suggest what recycling path each window should take, as well as answer the following questions:

How much glass is available in the built environment of project X based on information from the inventory/BIM models? [kg]

How much CO₂ can be saved, based on each possible scenario for the material?

The answers are then intended to be used for transportation and operational planning as well as giving information on how big the estimated volumes in and out of the flat glass treatment will be.

In this demonstration, we focused on the recyclable fraction and assessed values derived from the different inventory methods, including the CVFP-module, and compared them to the actual outcome of the physical recycling process at the Ragn-Sells facility in Örebro.

5. Results and Innovation

The initial weight measurements using the three different methods described in “Inventory of the Material Bank” are presented in Table 1. In the demonstration, the manual inventory was used as input for the categorization of the windows according to the following logic:

- Recycling w/o downgrading Scenario - **Green**
- Recycling Downgrading Scenario - **Blue (Laminated)**

The manual inventory used the instrument Glass Budy to identify laminated glass or glass with added film. These are categorized as blue. In the 3D scan method, manual counting was done when creating points of interest as described in “Inventory of the Material Bank”. As for the 3D scan + LiDAR, the existing BIM model provided the number of windows in the building to be dismantled.

Inventory method	Estimated count of windows: green	Estimated count of windows: blue	Process outcome: green	Process outcome: blue
Initial guess	200	20	127	10
Manual	137	1	127	10
3D scan	138	1	127	10
3D & LiDAR	138	1	127	10

Table 1. The results from the manual inventory and the inventory used by scanning are shown as number of windows.

As can be seen in table 1, there is a difference between the estimated count of windows and number of glass panes with and without lamination. Some of the green labeled windows had a film applied on them which caused technical issues in the pre-treatment. It shows the difficulty of getting the labeling right even though using the tool, Glass Budy.

In the “Vehicle over scale” step the full windows (glass + frame+pallet) were weighted, confirming a total of 8 406 kg from Teknikhöjden. The post pre-treatment weight was 3 828 kg glass, and this was the amount inserted into the quality assurance plant.

The outcome from the quality assurance plant was 3 481 kg cullet which is a raw material for glass production and not waste anymore. This corresponds to 91% of product compared to the pre-treatment weight. Further, 8% of the input weight was labeled “<8mm” and 1% was labeled “reject”.

The fraction “<8mm” is too small to be quality assured and was slightly higher than expected, but the windows from Teknikhöjden were too large to use in the normal pre-treatment process, thus another pre-treatment methods needed to be used which reduced the efficiency of the process somewhat.

Table 2 shows the final comparison between what was estimated in the different methods in the demonstration “inventory of the material bank” and the actual process output. For the sake of simplicity “glass downgrade” includes both reject and the “<8mm” fractions. The CO₂ estimations are calculated on the “Recyclable” fraction based on a template number.

Method	Glass – Recyclable (kg)	Glass – Downgrade (kg)	Est. CO2 savings (kg)	Accuracy % (Recyclable)
Initial guess	3105	N/A	1646	89%
Manual inventory	3887	22	2060	112%
3D scan	4096	22	2171	118%
3D & LiDAR	5148	22	2728	148%
Process output	3481	285	1844	100%

Table 2. The weight accuracy achieved from the manual inventory and the inventory used by scanning.

Manual inventory is very time-consuming as every single window needs to be investigated. An updated BIM model with detailed information about the actual number of panes and if there is any laminated glass in the window will

contribute the same information as a manual inventory in a digital format, ready to be used immediately. It is recommended to do a manual inventory of a few windows just to confirm the validity of the BIM-model.

A 3D scanning has the drawback of not providing information about the number of glass panes and if there is any laminated glass. It thus needs to be complemented with a manual measurement of the glass set up in the window. The size of the windows is provided, limiting the inventory to just the window configuration, making it a quicker process, but still time-consuming.

Each case will contribute to some unexpected deviations from the planned route. The windows from Teknikhögden were larger than possible to process in the pre-treatment machine, resulting in a slightly rougher treatment method. There were more windows with laminate than expected and thus less product. The demolition of the building took much longer than initially anticipated, and a few pallets remained on site making an extra transportation necessary. A planned upgrading of the recycling plant was more complicated than estimated, contributing to even more delays.

6. Contribution to Impacts

The demonstration “flat glass to flat glass” directly addresses the core barriers to circular construction identified in current practice: fragmented data, lack of standardization, and poor traceability. By tracking flat glass from a real building through dismantling, processing, and recycling, it demonstrates standardized, interoperable data capture across the main parts of the value chain, thereby contributing to several REINCARNATE impacts.

Scientific (I1-I6 — Medium):

The demo validates digitisation methods (I1) by linking inventory data with measured weights during processing, enabling assessment of circular potential. It supports interoperability (I2) by connecting audit data, ERP systems, and production data, creating an evidence-based case study (I6).

Societal (I7–I12 — Medium-High):

By enabling traceable reuse of glass cullet, the demo contributes to waste reduction and CO₂ savings (I7–I8) and demonstrates urban mining potential (I9). It also raises awareness among value-chain actors about practical circular workflows.

Techno-economic (I13–I18 — Medium):

The demonstration shows how digital traceability enables viable circular business models and new value chains (I13–I14), improves operational readiness toward deployment (I11), and supports scalable solutions for industry adoption (I16).

Overall, the demo translates abstract circular principles into a replicable, data-driven operational model for construction material reuse.

7. Replication and Next Steps

The demo flat glass to flat glass can be replicated with some prerequisites and conditions.

One requirement is to have the quality assurance step for flat glass cullet. The circular process and the downgraded material streams (residue and waste) depend on this quality assurance step and its conditions. The separation of glass from the frame is a prerequisite for the quality assurance process.

The inventory of windows must collect all required data to enable the division of windows into the recycling categories, see demonstration set up (green, blue, red with black as addition for hazardous waste). The extent of required data is listed in D1.4. A tool to test if the windows are laminated or not is needed since this is one of the required datapoints. To dismantle and handle the windows, competence in this area is required.

To enable CVFP, and the calculations made in the CVFP module in the CP-IM platform, all data specified in D1.4 needs to be collected. This is data from the different parts of the value chain. In this demonstration, the data has mainly been collected from ERP system, CRM system, and scales and thereafter noted in Excel sheets. As the next step, it is desirable to connect these systems to the CP-IM platform directly to avoid the manual work in the process and to automate data collection. APIs need to be developed by collecting data from the systems. How this can look is described in D1.4, The Digital flow.

It will be necessary to retrieve all data related to construction projects from the ERP and the weights from the process that accounts for the CO₂ savings. The calculation for CO₂ is today made manually, and these calculations are suitable for automation. One challenge to scaling CVFP will be to get actors aligned on using the ontology and to start using a CVFP-way of working. Changing habits has been harder than developing a system for handling data.

Incentives for different actors and transparency in the value chain will be necessary to get trust in the process and avoid greenwashing. This has been concluded in other research projects, such as Trace4Value.

8. References and Links

COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 1179/2012 of 10 December 2012 establishing criteria determining when glass cullet ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council.

Resuite.

Glass cullet ready for deliver to Saint-Gobain

Separation of glass from other materials in the window, pre-treatment.

Cullet from pre-treatment is loaded into the quality assurance plant.

Removal of big bag with product ready to send to Saint-Gobain

Special treatment of windows too large for ordinary pre-treatment.